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EFFICIENT DESIGN OF ZnO MICROCAVITY POLARITONS IN STRONG COUPLING REGIME AS FUTURE ENTANGLED PHOTON PAIRS SOURCE

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ABSTRACT

A design of ZnO-based microcavity is investigated and optimized in order to obtain microcavity polaritons in strong coupling regime. The A and B excitonic resonances specific to bulk ZnO are coupled with photon's cavity in a specific polarization condition and lead to up to three polaritonic branches. By means of detuning of the excitons-photons resonances, the engineered polaritonic branches allow for controlled polariton-polariton scattering and potentially to emission of entangled photon pairs. For this work we propose an efficient design of microcavity based on bulk ZnO with Bragg mirrors of 3 pairs of SiO₂/TiO₂, taking into account the technological limitations of the deposition methods of thin films and experimental values for the complex refractive indices of these films. The angle resolved reflectance of the microcavity structure is numerically computed. The polaritonic resonances are extracted from the reflectance spectrum. Therefore, dispersion polaritonic curves are obtained and proposed as input for further theoretical investigations.

Keywords: ZnO-microcavity, excitons-polaritons, entangled photons sources.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the search for ways of producing entangled photons, the building blocks of tomorrow's quantum communication protocols, has accelerated at an incredible pace. Entangled photon pairs are obtained by optical nonlinear effects in crystals, photonic crystal fibers and waveguides, and have been used to demonstrate quantum-secured communication [1]. The first entangled photon pair source was produced by down conversion in BBO nonlinear crystals [2]. A second approach for obtaining entanglement is based on four-wave mixing effect due to large third order nonlinear susceptibility χ^3 in some materials [3]. Experimentally, these sources are obtained in a laboratory environment using lasers, crystals, optical fibers, and bulky optomechanical components. From a fundamental point of view, this research stimulated the development of quantum information and quantum technologies. Technological efforts invested in the miniaturization of quantum sources made possible the production of devices compatible with space applications. Then, the first quantum-secured transmission of information was demonstrated via satellite [4]. The idea of a quantum internet is now on the list of future quantum technologies, and some progress was made in the direction of all-fiber quantum sources [5] compatible with the actual fiber optics infrastructure [6]. However, many promising applications remain under development, some challenges have to be overcome and improvements of the actual entangled photon pair sources are required: they are not adapted for integration in portable devices, some designs are sensitive to mechanical instabilities, the protocols need improvement of the quantum bit error rate (QBER). Then, it is clear that new ideas and solutions need to be investigated.

Polaritons in optical microcavities were intensively studied in recent years for their interesting fundamental properties including the possibility of obtaining Bose-Einstein Condensate (BEC) in semiconductors at room temperature and even polaritonic lasing [7]. An optical microcavity is a symmetric heterostructure formed by a series of thin films, similar to vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser (VCSEL) with three main regions: two Bragg mirrors and one active region in between, eventually with embedded quantum wells or quantum dots in the active region. Photons confined in the cavity are coupled with excitons from the semiconductor material in the cavity region. The main difference between microcavities and VCSELs consists in the strong coupling of the photons and excitons giving rise to the polaritonic modes in the microcavity. Polaritons are half-light, half-excitons, they are behaving as bosons, can be externally controlled by optical or electrical means, and can be converted to propagating optical qubits. These make the microcavity-based devices possible candidates for the next generation of quantum sources with several advantages: microcavities can be fabricated using the available semiconductor technologies, they have very small dimensions and are compatible with integrated optical circuits.

Some theoretical works propose microcavity designs as bright sources of hyper-entangled photon pairs [11, 12]. Using coupled microcavities, high generation rate of entangled photons was predicted in the proposed systems. Quantum entangled pairs of photons emitted from semiconductor structures were the first time experimentally demonstrated by Dousse et al. in coupled microcavities with InAs embedded quantum dots at 10 K [13]. When heterostructures are based on semiconductors such as GaAs or CdTe, the measurement requires cryogenic temperatures and shows low Raby

splitting [14, 15], mainly because of the phonon-polariton scattering in the cavity and the background noise generated by photoluminescence. Then, the material used for the active region and the pumping schemes are critical for obtaining the proper phase matching condition for parametric scattering and successful demonstration of the polaritonic entanglement at room temperature.

In this paper, we propose a design of a simple and efficient ZnO-based microcavity device used for creating strong photon-exciton coupling that could potentially lead to emission of entangled photon pairs due to the parametric polaritonic scattering process. We consider a single ZnO-bulk microcavity coupled ZnO excitons [16]. Such an approach allows for obtaining the polariton states in a strong coupling regime that originate from the coupling of the ZnO excitons with the cavity mode, all in the same cavity structure at room temperature. A similar polaritonic scattering mechanism as described by Portolan et al. in their work [11] is expected in order to generate pairs of entangled photons. However, instead of three microcavities coupled with the excitonic resonance in the active regions, we could consider two or three ZnO excitons coupled with a single microcavity. This approach allows for much more simple fabrication steps, avoiding the technological limitations related to the quality of thin film deposition when tens of layers for distributed Bragg reflectors (DBR) have to be grown for each of the coupled microcavities.

ZnO has been chosen as the active layer due to its high exciton binding energy of 60 meV that allows for the survival of excitons at room temperature. ZnO is a wurtzite type with a hexagonal crystalline structure. The three excitonic states A, B, and C specific to ZnO are active in different incident polarization conditions. A and B excitons are observed for incident excitation polarized parallel to the *c* axis of the hexagonal crystalline structure, while C exciton is active when incident light is polarized perpendicular to the *c* axis. If A and B excitons are simultaneously coupled with the microcavity resonance, up to three polaritonic branches are generated. Then, via controlled detuning of the cavity resonance with the excitonic resonance, a flexible engineering of the polaritonic scattering mechanism is possible.

2. Materials and Methods

The components of the microcavity and the numerical model are described in this section. The structure design consists of two Bragg mirrors obtained by deposition of pairs of dielectric thin films with alternances of refractive indices n_1 and n_2 and with optical thicknesses of $\lambda_0/4$, and the cavity, or the active zone with an optical thickness of multiples of $\lambda_0/2$, where λ_0 the designed central wavelength or the cavity resonance.

For the Bragg mirrors we have chosen the pairs of TiO₂-rutile and SiO₂, two of the most commonly used materials for high-reflectivity mirrors, usually found in laser mirrors that provide a high refractive index contrast $\Delta n = n_1 - n_2$ and consequently a high reflectance and large stop band. Also, these materials offer a low enough absorption coefficient in the spectral region of

interest 360-370 nm, where the ZnO excitons are observed at room temperature. The Bragg design is centered to the first excitonic resonance A at $\lambda_0 = 367$ nm.

The active medium of the planar cavity is made out of ZnO, a material that can sustain exciton resonances at room temperature, due to its high excitonic binding energy. The thickness of the cavity has been chosen as $3\lambda_0/2$. The structure is considered to have grown in our simulation on Si substrate, but also SiO₂ material can be used.

From a technological point of view, we have taken into account the use of environmentally friendly materials. Also, several other advantages could be mentioned, the chosen material can be easily deposited by available deposition technologies such as magnetron sputtering, pulsed laser deposition, electron-beam deposition. In our model, the wavelength-dependent refractive indices and absorption coefficients available in public databases and literature have been used for the considered thin films. The use of wavelength dependent material parameters, especially the absorption coefficient allows us to design an as much as realistic structure and to establish the optimal number of layers. Usually, for spectral ranges where materials exhibit low absorption coefficients, the number a DBR's layers is large enough, of the order of tens, in order to obtain the highest reflectance and large stopband. However, for the UV spectral range, the increased absorption coefficient will decrease the photon lifetime and the exciton-photon coupling in the cavity. Moreover, a large number of layers could be hard to deposit by the above-mentioned techniques, preserving at the same time the films' quality of the top layers. Once structural defects appear in the intermediate films during the deposition process, these defects propagate, the absorption will much increase, and then, all the structure could be compromised. With these technological limitations in mind, we studied the optimal design by minimizing the number of the dielectric pairs in the Bragg reflectors for which the strong coupling is still feasible.

For the numerical simulation of our structure, the transmission matrix method was used. In this model, the light wave propagation through the successive dielectric mediums is computed by considering every interface and the space between sequent interfaces. For each, a transfer matrix is evaluated taking into account the refractive indices, excitation wavelength, incident angle, polarization of the incident beam, and layer thickness. Then the field transformations through each one are computed, and the reflectance and transmittance of the entire structure are obtained. The corresponding transfer matrices are:

1. transfer matrix for interface:

$$M_I = \begin{pmatrix} 1/t & r/t \\ -r/t & 1/t \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

2. transfer matrix for spaces:

$$M_V = \begin{pmatrix} e^{ikz} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ikz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

3. transfer matrix for the entire structure:

$$M = \prod_{i=1}^N M_{I,i} \cdot M_{V,i} \quad (3)$$

where k is the wavevector of the light in the respective medium, z is the distance between two interfaces, and r and t are the reflectance and transmittance coefficients at the interface of two adjacent layers as they are described by the Fresnel relations on the s , p polarizations correspondingly:

$$r_s = \frac{n_1 \cos \theta_1 - n_2 \cos \theta_2}{n_1 \cos \theta_1 + n_2 \cos \theta_2} \quad (4)$$

$$r_p = \frac{n_2 \cos \theta_1 - n_1 \cos \theta_2}{n_1 \cos \theta_2 + n_2 \cos \theta_1} \quad (5)$$

$$t_s = \frac{2n_1 \cos \theta_1}{n_1 \cos \theta_1 + n_2 \cos \theta_2} \quad (6)$$

$$t_p = \frac{2n_1 \cos \theta_1}{n_1 \cos \theta_2 + n_2 \cos \theta_1} \quad (7)$$

Here n_1 and n_2 are the complex refractive indices for the media, and θ_1 and θ_2 are the incident and respectively the refraction angles at the interface.

The excitonic components are described below. The electrical susceptibility of the ZnO material close to the excitonic resonances for each excitonic state is mathematically expressed as below:

$$\chi_x(\epsilon_{0,x}, \epsilon) = \frac{\epsilon_{LT,x}}{\epsilon_{0,x} - \epsilon + i\gamma} \quad (8)$$

where X represents one of the ZnO excitons A or B, ϵ represents the energy of the light quanta that passes through the films, $\epsilon_{LT,x}$ is the longitudinal-transverse splitting energy for bulk excitons, $\epsilon_{0,x}$ is the excitonic resonance, and γ is the non-radiative broadening. The values of the materials constants ϵ_{LT} , ϵ_0 and γ are experimentally determined and are listed in Table 1.

Table 1.

Excitonic parameters for ZnO				
$\epsilon_{LT,A}$ (meV)	$\epsilon_{LT,B}$ (meV)	$\epsilon_{0,A}$ (meV)	$\epsilon_{0,B}$ (meV)	γ (meV)
1.5	11.5	3378.4	3384.6	10

Finally, to include the excitonic contribution to the complex refraction index for the microcavity we use the relation:

$$n_{MC} = n_{MC,real} \sqrt{1 + \chi} \quad (9)$$

where χ is the electrical susceptibilities as sum of all excitonic states. This is taken into account when the transfer matrices corresponding to the ZnO cavity layer is considered in the simulation.

3. Results and discussions

Experimentally, the dispersion curves of the microcavity polaritons are obtained by measuring the angle-resolved reflectance in the spectral range around the excitonic and cavity resonances. Due to the stop-band of the Bragg mirrors designed for a certain central wavelength, in our case $\lambda_0 = 367$ nm (3378.4 meV), the photons are trapped by the cavity. After a certain time – the cavity photons' lifetime – they could escape the cavity or can be absorbed within the active region of the cavity and generate excitons. The excitons have a finite lifetime, then will reemit photons that can escape the cavity or can be trapped back by the cavity and generate other excitons in a cyclic process. Such a cycling process gives rise to a quasiparticle inside de microcavity, the polariton, that is half-light and half-exciton, and has bosonic interaction characteristics. If the cavity photons and the excitons are at resonance, the strong coupling is achieved when the splitting of the polaritonic state is obtained. Then, instead of a single deep characteristic to the cavity resonance, the patterns of the polaritons in the reflectance spectrum are characterized by two deeps, one for the upper polariton and the second for the lower polariton, separated by a difference in energy named Raby splitting energy. In experiment, changing the incident angle of the excitation beam induce polaritons in cavity at different wavevectors. By following the angle resolved shifts of the polaritonic resonances in the reflectance spectra, the dispersion

curves of the polaritons are determined. In the numerical simulation, a similar protocol is involved. The reflectance spectra of the microcavity are computed using the model described in the previous paragraph. Then, from a series of reflectance spectra at different angles, the energies of the polaritonic deeps are obtained by deconvolution, and the polaritonic dispersion curves are recovered.

The generation of entangled photons in semiconductor microcavities directly depends on the polaritons scattering mechanism in the structure. Therefore, the first step of this research is to compute the polaritonic dispersion curves of the designed microcavity. The advantage of using semiconductor microcavities relies on the fact that the coupled photons-excitons can be controlled externally by optic or electronic means. Also, the parametric scattering processes can be controlled by engineering of the dispersion curve and by a proper design of the Bragg structure and cavity geometry.

The geometry simulated in our work consists of two Bragg mirrors each one formed by 3 pairs of TiO₂ and SiO₂ layers, with ZnO as cavity material between the two symmetric Bragg structures. The central cavity wavelength $\lambda_0 = 367$ nm is chosen to be in resonance with the exciton A of ZnO at room temperature. The refractive indexes for the materials at $\lambda_0 = 367$ nm are $n_{TiO_2} = 2.45$, $n_{SiO_2} = 1.49$, $n_{Si} = 6$ and $n_{ZnO} = 1.9$. These values are considered when physical thicknesses of the films are calculated as $l_0/4$ for the Bragg structure and $3l_0/2$ for the cavity. However, the wavelength dependent refractive indices and absorption coefficients are taken into account for the calculation of reflectance spectra in order to obtain realistic results [17-19]. The simulations have been done using the Python 3.9 programming language and a Python script has been written that uses the model described in the previous section.

In our simulations, the exciton-polariton states are obtained around the values of 3200, 3400, and 3450 meV for normal incidence, therefore for the DBRs we

need a stop-band with high reflectance to span the 3200-3500 meV range for normal incidence. Then, as the first step we design the half-Bragg mirror using a pattern of 3 pairs made of TiO_2 and SiO_2 in this order,

and then followed by a Si substrate, we achieve the energy-resolved reflectance dependence (see Figure 1.a). We observe that for the 3200-3500 meV interval the value of the reflectance is over 0.95, this distribution providing us with adequate results for our application.

Figure 1. Reflectance spectrum of a single DBR using 3 pairs of: (a) $\text{TiO}_2/\text{SiO}_2$ deposited of Si substrate. (b) $\text{SiO}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ deposited of Si substrate.

Alternatively, we investigate the reflectance of the symmetric Bragg mirror using a pattern of 3 pairs made of SiO_2 and TiO_2 in this order and then followed by a Si substrate, we achieve the energy-resolved reflectance dependence (see Figure 1.b). We observe that for the 3200-3500 meV interval, the interferential behavior strongly affects the stop-band shape, and it is caused by the presence of the Si substrate with a large refractive index compared to the other layers, giving for this particular case of film sequence a more antireflective behavior with a deep peak around 3000 meV. However, this distribution doesn't affect the final optical response since the complete structure involves more sequences of layers, but this feature indicates that the order of the

layers has to be verified and correctly chosen for the full design.

The complete structure of the device will consist of, as we have previously stated, 2 DBRs with the chosen $\text{TiO}_2/\text{SiO}_2$ sequences, a ZnO active medium, and a Si substrate. In the Figure 2.a we show the films' sequence of the structure by plotting the reference refractive indexes of the layers regarding their thicknesses and their position from the start of the device, as well as the dependence of the electric field in the device along its length. Here, the ZnO layer has an optical thickness of $3\lambda_0/2$ and the Si substrate has an optical thickness of $10\lambda_0$. However, since the effect is expected in the UV range, the thickness of the substrate is not relevant for this case.

Figure 2. (a) The sequence of thin films of the ZnO-based microcavity structure with 3 pairs of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{SiO}_2$ Bragg mirrors, the corresponding thickness and refractive index and electric field propagating in the structure. (b) Reflectance spectrum for a full microcavity structure with two excitons in the cavity.

Using the complete structure, we can numerically simulate the reflectance spectrum for normal incidence (see Figure 2.b) in the same way as for the DBRs previously presented. In polarized light, not all three excitons A, B, and C of ZnO are simultaneously active. We

assumed an incident excitation with polarization parallel to the c axis of the hexagonal crystalline structure of ZnO. Then, only the excitons A and B will be active in this configuration. In this simulation, we have introduced the two ZnO excitons with resonance energies

$\varepsilon_{0,B} = 3378.4$ meV and $\varepsilon_{0,B} = 3384.6$ meV. It can be observed from the graph that the peaks that we are most interested in, are the ones near 3200, 3400 and 3450 meV since others are just interferential patterns specific for the Bragg structure outside of the designed stop-band. The first two peaks of interest belong to the lower polaritonic branch and represent the excitonic-like resonance of the structure and the third one belongs to the upper polaritonic branch and represents the photonic-like resonance of the microcavity in a strong coupling regime.

Figure 3.a represents the angle-resolved reflectance plotted for different incidence angles varying between 0° and 45° with step of 1° . The plots are shifted vertically for better observation of the polariton peaks shift to higher energies as the angle increases. The ones that represent the excitonic-like branches are shown to asymptotically approach a certain energy value that

represents the exciton reference energy, while the photonic-like peak tends to continually increase without approaching a fixed value, this behavior is in line with the theoretical expectation of the strong coupling effect in microcavities. The angle dependences of the polaritonic peak energies (see Figure 3.b) extracted from the angle-resolved reflectance spectra can be also obtained experimentally and represent the polaritonic dispersion curves. The angles and the in-plane component of the wavevectors are linked by the relation:

$$k_{\parallel} = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta$$

where θ is the incident angle of the excitation beam and λ is the photons wavelength.

The polaritonic branches A, B and Ph in Figure 3.b correspond to strong coupling of A and B excitons with the cavity photons. We can better observe the different behavior of the excitonic-like branches and the asymptotic limits that they reach, compared with the photonic-like mode.

Figure 3. (a) Reflectance spectra for different incidence angles varying between 0° and 45° with step of 1° . (b) Polaritonic dispersion curves extracted from angle resolved reflectance spectra.

Figure 4.

(a) Reflectance spectra for different incidence angles varying between 0° and 45° with step of 1° with 5% detuning. (b) Polaritonic dispersion curves extracted from angle resolved reflectance spectra with 5% detuning.

In order to obtain entangled photons emitted by the structure, different parametric scattering scenarios could be imagined (see for ex. Ref. [12] and the references therein). By optical or electrical pumping, the exciton-polaritons are excited in the structure at a certain energy and wavevector on the dispersion curve. The

phonon-excitons scattering mechanism allows for the redistribution of the polaritons on the dispersion curve. This is an incoherent scattering process that induces an incoherent photoluminescence (PL) background emission competing with the parametric coherent photoemission [11]. In order to suppress the noncoherent PL

emission a proper pumping scheme and engineering of the polaritonic branches is required. The desired pumping scheme is experimentally obtained by using two polarized (or cross-polarized) beams incident at certain angles and beam wavelength. These are chosen in order to produce symmetrical polariton populations on excitonic branches, and by parametric scattering process a signal/idler pair of polaritonic emission while the energy and momentum are conserved. This mechanism is hard to be obtained if the curvature of the polariton branches is not suitable.

The first derivative of the curves is directly related to the polaritons mass and plays a role in the parametric scattering of the polaritons in the cavity [20]. Then, the shape of the polaritonic curves has to be controlled by some available methods, for example by detuning of the cavity resonance with respect to exciton resonance. This is achieved by modifying the layers' thicknesses of the microcavity structure. Figure 4 shows an example of the angle-resolved spectra (Figure 4a) and dispersion curves (Figure 4b) for a structure with a detuning of 5% percent from thickness at resonance, which correspond to a negative energy detuning of about -170 meV. Such polaritonic branches modification provide a certain flexibility in choosing the pumping scheme in terms in angle, wavelength and polarization of the incident beams. However, in order to accurately predict such experimental parameters, a detailed analysis of polariton-polariton scattering rate have to be computed for the chosen pumping scheme, which is not in the scope of the present paper.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we presented a ZnO microcavity structure as a candidate for a compact entangled photon source. We proposed a simple and efficient design for the creation of photon-exciton coupling at room temperature that could allow for parametric polaritonic scattering and emission of signal/idler pairs. The structure design consists of two Bragg mirrors with 3 pairs of SiO₂/TiO₂ films and $3\lambda_0/2$ ZnO bulk cavity. This configuration has been proposed taking into account the available deposition techniques, technological limitations, and wavelength dependent parameters, refractive indices, and absorption coefficients available in the literature in order to obtain an as much as realistic design. The number of the Bragg pairs was kept as low as possible, thus minimizing the absorption in the Bragg structure while the reflectance of the mirrors is optimized by choosing the materials with the highest refractive index contrast for low absorption coefficients. ZnO was used as the active material for obtaining the strong coupling at room temperature. This material provides up to 3 excitonic resonances that could be coupled with the cavity in different polarization configurations. This approach in designing our device brings an improvement compared to other structures with multiple coupled cavities as previously proposed. Through these ways, such design is easier to manufacture compared to other similar devices because of the reduction of the number of layers included, therefore reducing the structural defects and absorption. The polaritonic dispersion curves can be easily manipulated by detuning, in order

to optimize the pumping scheme and the parametric polaritonic scattering. Future works have to be dedicated to the investigation of the most efficient pumping schemes taking into account the polariton-polariton scattering rates to provide a complete design of microcavity that could provide emission of entangled photons.

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References

1. Anton Zeilinger, Light for the quantum. Entangled photons and their applications: a very personal perspective, *Phys. Scr.* 92 072501 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1402-4896/aa736d>.
2. Kwiat P et al, New high-intensity source of polarization-entangled photon pairs *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 75, 4337-4341 (1995). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.75.4337>.
3. O Alibart et al. Photon pair generation using four-wave mixing in a microstructured fibre: theory versus experiment, *New J. Phys.* 8, 67 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/8/5/067>.
4. Elizabeth Gibney, Chinese satellite is one giant step for the quantum internet, *Nature* 535, 478 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/535478a>.
5. M. Fiorentino et al. All-fiber photon-pair source for quantum communications, *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters* 14 (7). 983-985 (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1109/LPT.2002.1012406>.
6. Christensen, et al. All-fiber photon-pair source at telecom wavelengths. *Proceedings of SPIE* 10118 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2252019>.
7. S. Christopoulos et al. Room-Temperature Polariton Lasing in Semiconductor Microcavities, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 98, 126405 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.98.126405>.
8. C. Ciuti, Branch-entangled polariton pairs in planar microcavities and photonic wires, *Phys. Rev. B* 69, 245304 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.69.245304>
9. Joanna M. Zajac et al. Parametric scattering of microcavity polaritons into ghost branches, *Phys. Rev. B* 92, 165305 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.92.165305>.
10. Mathias Sassermaann et al. Quantum statistics of polariton parametric interactions, Permanent ID: arXiv:1808.01127 (2018). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.01127>

11. S. Portolan et al. Generation of hyper-entangled photon pairs in coupled microcavities, *New Journal of Physics* 16, 063030 (2014). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/16/6/063030>.
12. L. Einkemmer et al. Polarization entanglement generation in microcavity polariton devices, *Physica status solidi (b)* 252 (8) 1749-1756 (2015). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201451704>.
13. Adrien Dousse et al., Ultrabright source of entangled photon pairs *Nature* 466, 217–220 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09148>.
14. C. Grossmann et al. Strong coupling at room temperature in ultracompact flexible metallic microcavities, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 102, 011118 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4773881>.
15. Huang R et al. Exciton-polariton lasing and amplification based on exciton–exciton scattering in CdTe microcavity quantum wells. *Phys Rev B* 65, 165314 (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.65.165314>.
16. Bernard Gil, Oscillator strengths of A, B, and C excitons in ZnO films, *Phys. Rev. B* 64, 201310(R) (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.64.201310>.
17. S. Sarkar, V. Gupta, M. Kumar, J. Schubert, P.T. Probst, J. Joseph, T.A.F. König, Hybridized guided-mode resonances via colloidal plasmonic self-assembled grating, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 11, 13752-13760 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b20535>.
18. L. Gao, F. Lemarchand, M. Lequime. Refractive index determination of SiO₂ layer in the UV/Vis/NIR range: spectrophotometric reverse engineering on single and bi-layer designs, *J. Europ. Opt. Soc. Rap. Public.* 8, 13010 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.2971/jeos.2013.13010>.
19. O. Aguilar, S. de Castro, M. P. F. Godoy, M. R. S. Dias. Optoelectronic characterization of Zn_{1-x}Cd_xO thin films as an alternative to photonic crystals in organic solar cells, *Opt. Mater. Express* 9, 3638-3648 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1364/OME.9.003638>.
20. Olivier Bleu, Guangyao Li, Jesper Levinsen, and Meera M. Parish, *Phys. Rev. Research* 2, 043185 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.2.043185>.